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FACTORS THAT IMPACT ON EFFECTIVE TEACHING ENGLISH LEXIS

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Abstract: *This research examines a wide range of factors that impact on teaching English vocabulary to the students. The importance of students’ age, cultural context, level of English language should be taken into consideration in order to achieve success in Second Language acquisition. It explores various teaching methodologies which creates student-centered environment rather than teacher-centered one. The article highlights the significance of learning atmosphere, motivation and support for the students in learning English vocabulary. Moreover, it offers an understandable framework for English teachers who can learn methods to teach English lexis to the diverse students.*

Key words: *English lexis, vocabulary acquisition, teaching methodologies, communicative approaches, task-based learning, learning environment, student motivation, intrinsic motivation, authentic context, multimodal learning, retention, educational settings, cultural context, background knowledge.*

Introduction:

Effective vocabulary teaching can open a wide door for English learners to enhance their four language skills namely, Reading, Listening, Writing and Speaking. Being aware of various factors that impact on the efficiency of vocabulary acquisition can increase teaching methodologies. Communicative approaches and task-based strategies can undoubtedly enhance students’ knowledge of lexis and also it creates a supportive learning environment.

Literature Review

A great number of researches were done in teaching vocabulary effectively. Over years, different types of methodologies were created by many researchers and scientists. Johnson (2018) and Richards & Schmidt (2010) emphasized that student engagement and retention can greatly increase their vocabulary which is a cornerstone for other language skills. According to Willis (1996) the tasks facilitate the process of learning vocabulary by motivating students and arising interest in them to learn the new words. Ellis (2003) stated that tasks can give chances to the students for both utilization of structural and functional language. Dornyei (2001) points out that supportive and friendly atmosphere in the classroom can boost students’ motivation. Other researchers like Ryan and Deci (2000) stated that students engagement can impact significantly on learning vocabulary.

Utilization of combination of learning approaches can combine effortlessly visual, auditory and kinesthetic stimuli which can assist in learning vocabulary. Plass et al.(2014) suggested that employing different teaching methods can enhance students’ comprehension and retention. Knowing cultural backgrounds of the students can facilitate understanding and learning new vocabulary without any effort.

Teaching English vocabulary is one of the most challenging tasks for the educators. However, using a wide range of interactive methods during the lessons can not only enhance students' motivation, but also facilitates the process of teaching. Students can easily be exposed to learning new words by doing interesting tasks which are distributed by the educators. In creating and opting the teaching materials teachers should consider their learners' age, interests, backgrounds and language proficiency. If students own high proficiency in their native language they can easily enhance other foreign languages and their grasping will help them to learn them quickly. According to the statistics younger learners memorize the new words faster and easier compared to elder ones. Since their ability of learning something new stands in higher rank than older students.

Educators should choose authentic materials that belong to the students' cultural background. By doing this students' interests can significantly arise and learning vocabulary can be effortless for them. Communicative approach is widely used in the world by the educators, since it helps them to use the new words in ever day life by communicating with their peers. Moreover, task-based learning offers a great number of opportunities to the language learners demanding them to use specific given words by making scenarios or dialogues.

Some researchers emphasized the importance of classroom setting which creates an atmosphere for collaboration. Teamwork is a key to success in teaching a new vocabulary to the diverse students which is one of the challenges that educators face during the process of teaching. Teachers' support especially for the beginners is crucial which make the students feel safe. In such kind of environment, they will not be afraid of doing any mistakes, instead they will be risk-takers. Diverse teaching materials such as books, audiovisual aids and digital tools can be great assistances for the educators in teaching a second language lexis.

Authentic materials can help them to learn the new words by real-world and they will learn them during the lessons. Educators can play them videos related to their topic of the lesson on U Tube which is widely used by educators in the developed countries successfully. Educators should create some tasks or exercises to the videos they opted themselves. For doing this they should be professional in their field. Teaching new vocabulary is significant in enhancing learners language proficiency, therefore majority of the learners aim to improve their vocabulary day by day. Therefore, educators ought to pay attention to the selection of the new words carefully. They should opt the lexis related to the topic of the lesson considering the learners' age and level proficiency. Furthermore, teaching the students how to set goals in language learning can lead them to gain success in second language acquisition. Giving rewards are essential to motivate the learners in pursuing vocabulary learning. Celebrations of the students' achievements can make them learn more and more words by being eager to get a reward no matter how small. Implementation of the various games during the lessons can assist to make a friendly atmosphere where the learners can be engaged with their peers.

Contextual learning can help the learners to learn the new words in a meaningful context. Stories with new words in bold can facilitate comprehension of the students paying attention to their functions and strengthens retention. Graphic organizers and word maps are should be made by the learners themselves in collaboration which in turns only leads them to achieve success in learning the new words in teams. Synonyms, antonyms and definitions are also beneficial for the learners to memorize dozens of words in a day. However, only memorizing the new words can be daunting for the students, therefore the educators should bear in their minds teaching the new words in context can facilitate the process of learning the new vocabulary and they can practice them in their real life

situations in the future. Different activities such as writing a story, a book review or an essay make them use the learned new words in their writing.

Conclusion

Effective teaching English lexis involves several factors such as students' background, interactive activities, the friendly environment, retention and student motivation. By taking into consideration the educators can facilitate the learning process and create beneficial vocabulary learning experience which can serve only for better in the future. Educators should be professional in opting appropriate teaching materials to employ during the lessons by considering the students' age, cultural background and language proficiency level. Utilization of social media can undoubtedly enhance students' motivation and interest to learning the new vocabulary which in turn can lead to achieve success in a long journey called "Second Language Acquisition".

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